

**ŞULĤ, AN ISLAMIC ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE
RESOLUTION MODEL AND ITS RELEVANCE TO INTER-
FAITH CRISES IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstracts

Inter-religious crises remain a recurring challenge in multi-religious societies, particularly in contexts where religious diversity intersects with historical grievances, political contestations, and social fragmentation. In Nigeria, Osun State represents a relatively peaceful yet religiously diverse setting where sporadic inter-faith tensions underscore the need for culturally resonant and sustainable conflict resolution mechanisms as the inter-faith encounters have resulted in loss of lives, destruction of properties, and social discordance which was orchestrated by the battle for recognition, supremacy, and relevance. This paper examines *Şulĥ*, an Islamic model of alternative dispute resolution, as a viable framework for managing and preventing inter-faith crises in plural societies. Employing a qualitative research design, the study integrates doctrinal analysis of Islamic legal principles **with** empirical content analysis of seven inter-faith conflict cases in Osun State, drawn from in-depth interviews with religious leaders, community actors, and traditional authorities in Eḍe, Iwo, Osogbo, and Ile-Ife. The paper contributes to

scholarship on Islamic Alternative Dispute Resolution and interfaith peacebuilding by offering an empirically grounded analytical model that bridges Islamic legal theory, constitutional pluralism, and lived inter-religious relations in Nigeria.

Keywords: Inter-faith Conflicts; Şulh; Islamic Conflict Resolution; Osun State; Religious Pluralism; Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR).

Introduction

Osun is one of the six states in southwest Nigeria, others are Oyo, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo and Ekiti. Osun State is situated within latitudes 60 551 and 80 101 North and longitudes 30 551 and 5 0 051 East of Southwestern Nigeria, covering an estimated area of 8,602 square kilometers. Created on August, 1991 along with eight others by the regime of the former Nigeria President, Ibrahim Babangida, Osun state was carved out of the former Oyo State. As a result of this, it became one of the component units of Nigeria and one of the Yoruba-speaking states. The State was so named because of the importance the people attached to the Osun River, a mermaid river believed to be a goddess of fertility and a major goddesses revered and celebrated in August every year by the people of Osun State¹.

Upon its creation as a state, Osun State consist of thirty Local Government Areas with three senatorial districts: Osun West, Osun Central and Osun East. Each Senatorial district has ten Local Government Areas. Osun West consists of Aiyedaade, Aiyedire, Ede North and South, Ejigbo, Egbedore, Irewole, Isokan, Iwo and Ola-Oluwa Local Government Areas; Osun Central has Boripe, Boluwaduro, Ifedayo, Ifelodun, Ila, Irepodun, Odo-Otin, Olorunda, Orolu and Osogbo; while Osun East consists of Atakumosa East and West, Ife Central, East, North and South, Ilesa East and West, Obokun and Oriade Local Government Areas.

Apart from Osogbo, the state capital, the State has many notable towns with significant population of many religious adherents. The town like Ile-Ife, Ede, Iwo, Ikirun, Iragbiji, Ejigbo, Erin-Osun, Ilesa, Okuku, Inisa, Ila Orangun, Gbongan, Ilobu, Ifon-Osun, Ijabe, Konta, Obaagun, Ikire, Orile-Owu², etc.

The introduction of Islam in the area now called Osun State cannot be mentioned in isolation from the advent of Islam in Yoruba land because the advent of Islam in Osun State came through the successful emergence of Islam in Yoruba land. In fact for its relevance to this work, there is a need to briefly trace the history of its emergence in Yorubaland and its sociological interaction with the Yoruba traditional religion and Christianity with a view to comprehending the background of inter-faith relations generally in Yorubaland and Osun State in particular.

The spread and development of Islam in Yoruba land has attracted a sufficient attention of scholars. For emphasis, by the 17th century, Yorubaland have had contact with the already Islamized areas (Songhai, Mali), especially those to the

North-West of Yorubaland, through the activities of traders, settlers, preachers, and mendicants. Thus by the 18th Century, Islam had spread to strategic places³. It must be emphasised that the foremost cities in Osun State that had earlier contact with Islam are Ede, Osogbo, Iwo, Ikirun⁴, and many other places in the state now called Osun State. Nevertheless, the focus of this study is to examine the religious encounters in Osun State.

Although Osun State is a pluralistic society in the Southwest Nigeria with a larger Muslim population and a considerable Christian population, yet Traditional Religious practices is prominent in the state. There are many Muslims and Christians who practice syncretism by participating in the annual festival celebrations of the indigenous Traditional Religions such as the Osun Osogbo festival of Osun State⁵. While there are also devout Muslims in the State, for instance when there was a demand that the affairs of the Muslims of Southwest Nigeria be guided by the *Sharī'ah*, the cause was championed by the League of Imams and Alfas of Osun State who made public demand for their needs.

The demand of the League of Imams and Alfas of Osun State was contained in the memorandum submitted to the Osun State House of Assembly in December, 1999 signed by their Chairman, late Alhaji Mustafa Ajisafe, the late Chief Imam of Osogboland. The memorandum refers to the application of *Sharī'ah* during the pre-colonial era in Yorubaland, particularly in Ede, Iwo and Ikirun before *Sharī'ah* was abolished by the British. Different Islamic organisations or groups like MSSN, Ansarud-Din, NACOMYO, etc, in the state organised a series of lectures, symposia and rallies on the establishment of *Sharī'ah* as well as the Muslim Community of Osun State. This agitation reveals more about how devout the Muslim residents of Osun State are⁶. It must be emphasised that pluralism and diversity are core values in Islamic tradition and religion. The Qur'an recognizes diversity and tolerance of differences based on gender⁷; complexion, language⁸; beliefs and ranks⁹. Harmony between the different social grouping and communities is praised, and competition and control of any person by another is condemned¹⁰.

Religious Conflicts, Freedom, And Its Practice

The word “conflict” is derived from the Latin word *confligere*, which means to “strike together.” Conflict is as old as mankind, and it is a salient feature of the human society because disagreement is experienced at all levels of the society and characterized by clash, contention, confrontation, battle, struggle, controversy, or quarrel, to be contrary or to be at variance, it may either be violent or non-violent¹¹.

Conflict arises from differences in interests, ideas, ideologies, orientations, beliefs and perceptions. It is observed that conflict is of different kinds and is classified based on the intensity of violence and elements that are involved in the conflict like social class, ethnic, groups, religious group, racial group, etc.¹² Religious conflicts

convey the meaning of disagreement between two or more people of either same or different religious groups. Inter-religious conflicts imply disputes or tensions between people of different religious beliefs.

It is instructive to observe that religious crises in pluralistic societies often emerge not from the mere existence of freedom of religion, but from contested and competing claims surrounding its exercise. Individuals and groups frequently seek to assert their constitutionally and internationally protected right to freedom of thought, conscience, and religion, a right guaranteed under numerous international legal instruments, including the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), the African (Banjul) Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), the Arab Charter on Human rights (ACHR) 2004, and the American Convention on Human Rights.¹³ This freedom is also granted by the Nigerian Constitution as one of the fundamental rights as provided for under the provisions of Section 38 of the 1999 Constitution (as amended).

Religious freedom, as a fundamental human right, encompasses the freedom of expression and association. This includes the liberty to assemble with others and practice one's religious traditions without interference. The protection of religious freedom is upheld by the constitution and various laws and policies. The constitution specifically states that the government "shall not adopt any religion as State Religion"¹⁴. However, in contexts where regulatory frameworks and conciliatory mechanisms are weak, absent or seen as merely superficial, such assertions may escalate into inter-religious tensions and open conflict.

In Islam, freedom of religion is a fundamental human right and guaranteed throughout history. Individuals have the right to freedom of thought, conscience, and religion, which includes the freedom to express their religion through teaching, practice, worship, and observance in both public and private settings. The guarantee of religious freedom is seen in the Qur'anic principle of the absence of compulsion in religion.¹⁵ It was reported that the Prophet, in his exercise of freedom of religion, received about 60 Christians delegates from *Najran*, they ate, slept and were even permitted to pray in the Prophet's Mosque in *Madinah*¹⁶. Although the meaning of Qur'an 2:256 is general, yet it was revealed because of the *Ansar* (Muslims residents of Madinah)¹⁷

This prohibition of forceful acceptance of religion shows that every human being has the right to accept a religion and belief of his or her choice. Islam as a social order prohibits its follower to force Islam on others. Consequently, the verse of no compulsion in religion, has become a principle of religious freedom respected by Muslim rulers throughout the Ages. God grants human being will to make choices and be responsible for their decision. Thus, religious dictatorship is prohibited and

religious pluralism is a divine arrangement¹⁸. Islam equally recognises that the unrestricted or absolutist exercise of fundamental rights may result in the infringement of the rights of others. In the sensitive sphere of religious expression, such unregulated assertions may precipitate inter-religious tensions and, in extreme cases, religious crises. This normative restraint is clearly articulated in the Qur'ān where Allah prohibits statements or conducts that may likely constitute insult or denigration towards other people's faith as this may trigger hostile reciprocation¹⁹. By this prohibition, Islamic law seeks to prevent the escalation of religious violence, safeguard communal security, and foster peaceful coexistence among adherents of diverse religious traditions.

Generally, human rights in Islam are clearly stated in the interests of humanity and the concept of religious freedom cannot be discussed in isolation without human rights, especially the right to think and follow the tendencies of conscience. Among all human rights, the right of freedom of religion is the most important one. Along with the freedom of conviction and freedom of conscience, Islam has given the right to the individual that his religious sentiments will be given due respect, and nothing will be said or done which may encroach upon this right²⁰.

Ṣulḥ, An Islamic Alternative Dispute Resolution Model

The Islamic concept of *Ṣulḥ* implies reconciliation or amicable settlement of disputes outside the courtroom. Its goal is to end conflict and encourage peace among both individuals and the community. Hence, an Islamic model of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR). *Ṣulḥ* is the amicable settlement of disputes through good faith negotiation, conciliation/mediation, peace-making, and even extends to compromise of action. It is a process of restoring justice amicably among the disputants. The term *Ṣulḥ* has been used to refer to the process of restorative justice, peacemaking, and a method of resolving dispute amicably without litigation.

In *Shari'ah*, *Ṣulḥ* is a settlement grounded upon compromise negotiated by the disputants themselves or with the help of a third party. Therefore, it is the actual outcome of the reconciliatory processes undertaken to resolve a dispute, i.e., the agreement entered into by the disputants. *Ṣulḥ* represents a method of conflict resolution in the Islamic legal system and its process is facilitated by either a *Qadi* or prominent member of the family or community. However, it involves the principles of counseling, advising and arbitration. During the process, the facilitator assists the parties as they attempt to reach a voluntary settlement. The facilitator can suggest various settlement proposals, but cannot force a final agreement on the parties. Once the parties ultimately reach a settlement, it becomes a binding judgment. Therefore, the subject matter of *Ṣulḥ* must be lawful. The Prophet (SAW) is reported to have said that *Ṣulḥ* is permissible among the Muslims except the one which makes the unlawful as lawful and which makes the unlawful

as lawful. Muslims are bound by their promises except promises that permit the unlawful as lawful and the lawful as unlawful²¹.

The concept of *Ṣulḥ* is presented by the Qur'an and exemplified by the Prophet (SAW) where its legality is derived as a means of settling all civil matters which include marital disputes, commercial disputes, communal disputes, religious disputes²², etc. It is developed through the *ijma and ijtihad* of the Muslim jurists as an aspect of Islamic system of administration of justice. There are different methods of accomplishing *Ṣulḥ* because it is available to resolve all manner of civil disputes and well suited for resolving the cross-cultural and inter-faith disputes. Similarly, for the parties to allow peace to reign, they must be ready to make some compromises in trying to resolve cross-cultural or religious disputes as this was aptly demonstrated by the Prophet (SAW) during the *Ṣulḥ of Hudaibiyyah* when there was a dispute between the Muslims and non-Muslims over their entrance to Makkah to perform Umrah, settlement agreement was reached. However, the terms of settlement were not in favour of the Muslims but the Prophet had to compromise for peace to prevail²³.

Furthermore, *Ṣulḥ* is adopted in all civil matters as a method of dispute resolution through a third party or by the disputing parties under the guidance of specific conditions of disclosure of the truth, intention of reconciliation and respecting the settlement agreement. Once the conflicting parties arrange a mutual agreement so that the case is solved amicably, then the victim or the heirs of the victim will then get fair compensation for the harm caused by the offender. This is different from the general criminal cases settlement in which the offender or defendant/accused has no right to settle the case amicably once he got arrested. Then, the case will be between the state (represented by the prosecutor) and the accused (the offender). Simply to say, the offender is not allowed to arrange *Ṣulḥ* with the victim or the heirs of the victim²⁴. The practice of *Ṣulḥ* requires normative and procedural foundations in form of principles through which it operates as an effective means of reconciliation, justice, and peaceful coexistence. These principles define the ethical boundaries, methodological approaches, and mechanisms that ensure reconciliation reflects Islamic legal norms and dynamics of societal realities, they include:

Affirmation of Religious Plurality and Freedom of Conscience

The principles of *Ṣulḥ* as an Islamic model of ADR are deeply rooted in the Qur'an and the Sunnah. Among the most fundamental of these principles is the affirmation of religious plurality and the recognition of freedom of conscience as an inherent aspect of human existence. This principle constitutes the normative foundation upon which peaceful coexistence and sustainable reconciliation in pluralistic societies are constructed. Allah, in Qur'an 5:48 explicitly acknowledges religious

diversity as part of the divine order and a manifestation of divine wisdom. Besides, the autonomy of religion is unequivocally reiterated in the provisions of Qur'an 10:99 implying that faith cannot be imposed through coercion but through personal conviction.

From the perspective of *Ṣulḥ*, the recognition of religious autonomy is a practical prerequisite for peaceful dispute resolution. In multi-religious societies, interfaith conflicts often arise from attempts to assert religious superiority or restrict the rights of others. Accordingly, the affirmation of religious plurality and freedom of conscience constitutes the first procedural and normative stage of *Ṣulḥ* in interfaith contexts. It creates the moral and legal environment in which dialogue, negotiation, and reconciliation can meaningfully occur.

Preventive Ethics of Respect and Non-Provocation

Another fundamental principle of *Ṣulḥ* in Islamic jurisprudence is the adoption of preventive measures aimed at safeguarding interfaith harmony through respect for the religious beliefs and symbols. Islam does not merely prescribe reconciliation after the eruption of conflict; it also establishes normative ethical boundaries designed to prevent the emergence and escalation of religious tensions in the first place.

The provisions of Qur'an 6:108 explicitly prohibits Muslims from engaging in speech or conduct that may ridicule or demean the religious beliefs of others where Allah Says:

وَلَا تَسُبُّوا الَّذِينَ يَدْعُونَ مِنْ دُونِ اللَّهِ فَيَسُبُّوا اللَّهَ عَدْوًا بِغَيْرِ عِلْمٍ كَذَلِكَ زَيْنًا لِكُلِّ أُمَّةٍ عَمَلُهُمْ ثُمَّ إِلَىٰ رَبِّهِمْ مَرْجِعُهُمْ فَيُنَبِّئُهُمْ بِمَا كَانُوا يَعْمَلُونَ

And do not insult those they invoke other than Allāh, lest they insult Allāh in enmity without knowledge. Thus We have made pleasing to every community their deeds. Then to their Lord is their return, and He will inform them about what they used to do.

The verse above articulates a profound preventive logic within Islamic legal and ethical thought. It recognises that religious identity occupies a deeply emotional and symbolic space in human consciousness and that derogatory remarks against sacred beliefs are likely to provoke reciprocal hostility. By prohibiting such conduct, the Qur'an establishes a principle of restraint and mutual respect as essential prerequisites for peaceful coexistence in multi-religious societies.

Moreover, the concluding part of Qur'an 6:108 "Thus We have made pleasing to every community their deeds..." extends this preventive ethic beyond Muslims to

encompass others in a multi-religious society where religious communities coexist within shared social spaces. It implies that each faith tradition possesses its own sacred values, which must be respected within the broader context of societal coexistence. This principle, prevents provocative speech and sacrilegious conduct serves as an early-stage mechanism for conflict management, ensures that interfaith disputes are addressed before they escalate into open hostility, and resonates with the juristic principle that harm (*darar*) must be prevented before it occurs, a maxim that underlies many Islamic legal rulings concerning public order and social harmony.

Preference for Peaceful Settlement and Commitment to Reconciliation

A further foundational principle of *Ṣulḥ* in Islamic jurisprudence is the normative preference for peace, dialogue, and reconciliation over confrontation and violence. Islam prioritises negotiated settlement and de-escalation as primary responses to conflict, including disputes arising within interfaith contexts. Allah prefers peaceful negotiations when adversaries propose peace. This is articulated in the provisions of Qur'an 8:61, Allah Says:

﴿وَإِنْ جَنَحُوا لِلسَّلْمِ فَاجْنَحْ لَهَا وَتَوَكَّلْ عَلَى اللَّهِ إِنَّهُ هُوَ السَّمِيعُ الْعَلِيمُ﴾

And if they incline to peace, then incline to it [also] and rely upon Allāh. Indeed, it is He who is the Hearing, the Knowing. This verse establishes a binding legal and moral obligation upon Muslims to respond positively to genuine initiatives for peace. *Ibn Kathīr*, in his commentary on Qur'an 8:61, explains that the Prophet Muḥammad (SAW) acted upon this principle during the Treaty of al-Ḥudaybiyyah, when the Quraysh expressed their willingness to suspend hostilities and proposed terms of peace. The Prophet accepted the offer thereby demonstrating that the pursuit of reconciliation takes precedence over immediate military or political gains and underscores the significance of *Ṣulḥ* as a strategic instrument for sustainable peace²⁵.

Ethical Interfaith Dialogue

A fundamentally actionable principle of *Ṣulḥ* in the management of interfaith conflicts is the obligation of ethical dialogue. Within Islamic jurisprudence, dialogue is not merely a pragmatic strategy but a normative method of engagement that transforms inter-religious interaction from confrontation to constructive communication. Thus, interfaith dialogue constitutes a procedural pillar of *Ṣulḥ*, enabling disputing religious communities to articulate grievances, negotiate differences, and build sustainable peaceful coexistence. Allah allows dialogical engagement with adherents of other faith in Qur'an 3:64 on the basis of shared

ethical and theological commonalities while acknowledging doctrinal differences. Allah Says:

قُلْ يَا أَهْلَ الْكِتَابِ تَعَالَوْا إِلَى كَلِمَةٍ سَوَاءٍ بَيْنَنَا وَبَيْنَكُمْ أَلَّا نَعْبُدَ إِلَّا اللَّهَ وَلَا نُشْرِكَ بِهِ شَيْئًا وَلَا يَتَّخِذَ بَعْضُنَا بَعْضًا أَرْبَابًا مِّنْ دُونِ اللَّهِ فَإِن تَوَلَّوْا فَقُولُوا اشْهَدُوا بِأَنَّا مُسْلِمُونَ

Say, "O People of the Scripture, come to a word that is equitable between us and you - that we will not worship except Allāh and not associate anything with Him and not take one another as lords instead of Allāh." But if they turn away, then say, "Bear witness that we are Muslims [submitting to Him]."

The provisions of the above verse demonstrate that Islamic engagement with other religious communities is premised on reasoned discourse, mutual recognition, and the pursuit of common ground. Beyond the invitation to dialogue, the Qur'an also prescribes the normative ethics governing such dialogue. Qur'an 16:125 commands Muslims to engage others with wisdom, moral persuasion, and intellectual civility. Similarly, Qur'an 29: 46 further elaborates the modalities of interfaith engagement by stipulating a nuanced framework that balances tolerance with justice. It affirms peaceful dialogue as the normative mode of engagement while recognising the legitimacy of resistance to aggression and injustice. Thus, Islam distinguishes between conflict arising from religious difference and conflict arising from oppression or hostility. The Qur'an consistently condemns aggression and violence, declaring that God does not love aggressors (Qur'an 2:190), and simultaneously obligates Muslims to cease hostilities when adversaries incline toward peace (Qur'an 2:192; 8:61).

Historically, the Prophetic practice further exemplifies this dialogical approach. The Prophet Muḥammad (SAW) welcomed and engaged in dialogue with Christian delegations from *Najrān* and other non-Muslim communities, thereby institutionalising dialogue as a legitimate and effective instrument of peaceful coexistence. In practical terms, the dialogical stage of *Ṣulḥ* entails the convening of disputing parties or their representatives including recognised religious institutions, community leaders, and mediators to articulate grievances and negotiate pathways toward reconciliation as established by the provisions of Qur'an 4:35. Although Q. 4:35 was revealed in the context of matrimonial disputes, yet it articulates a broader jurisprudential principle applicable to communal and interfaith conflicts which is the necessity of structured mediation and representative dialogue in the pursuit of reconciliation.

Inter-Religious Encounters in Osun State

The 2014 Eegun Ogundeji and Qamarudeen Islamic Society in Iwo

The 2014 inter-religious conflict in Ile Oweeru, Iwo, occurred during the annual Eegun Ogundeji masquerade festival, a culturally and religiously significant event in Iwo. Masquerade processions in Yorubaland are highly ritualized, intersecting with neighborhoods predominantly inhabited by adherents of other faiths. In this instance, the conflict was triggered by the decision to extend the masquerade procession beyond its customary boundaries, despite prior warnings, especially in areas with a Muslim majority.²⁶ The decision to ignore these warnings triggered tension between the traditional worshippers and members of the Qamarudeen Islamic Society which has historically experienced confrontations with some masquerade groups, notably Eegun Kelebe, Eegun Fopomoyo, and the prominent Eegun Sokoti, largely due to the Qamarudeen Islamic Society's ideological stance encapsulated in the slogan "*kò sẹ̀bọ, kò s'òdògùn*" (no idol worship, no charms). Such historical tensions created a backdrop in which the procession could easily be misinterpreted as a deliberate provocation. The escalation of the conflict was influenced by symbolic actions of ringing a bell by one of the masquerade followers, an act not traditionally associated with Eegun Ogundeji, was interpreted by members of the Islamic society as the characteristic signal of Eegun Sokoti, a group known for antagonism toward the society.²⁷ It led to the disruption of the festival, physical assaults on masquerade followers, and burning the masquerade regalia. Institutional responses to the conflict involved both traditional authority and formal judicial processes.²⁸

Religious Rights and Institutional Breach at Bowen University, Iwo

Inter-religious tensions in Iwo, particularly between Muslim and Christian communities, have majorly centered around educational and institutional developments. Around 1990, the Baptist Church spearheaded efforts to establish a private university for the development of Iwo, mobilizing financial contributions from across the town. Given that the Muslim population constituted a significant majority in Iwo, a considerable proportion of the financial support originated from Muslim contributors, coordinated through the town's mosques, each of which received receipts to document contributions intended for land acquisition and university establishment. The establishment of the university occurred during the reign of Oba Atadese, who had previously been a member of the Baptist Church before reverting to Islam. Leveraging both religious influence and governmental support, the university successfully acquired approximately 1,500 hectares of land and was eventually established as Bowen University, with formal assurances that it would remain religiously non-partisan by ensuring the freedom of Muslim staff and students to practice their faith.

Subsequent deviations from these agreements led to escalating tensions. By 2001, there was restrictions on Muslim religious practice and the use of Hijab, which were perceived as violations of the initial settlement. The situation intensified when two Muslim students, children of a prominent community member, were reportedly forced to attend Baptist fellowship programs and were later expelled for non-compliance²⁹. In response, the Ta'awunil Muslimīn Iwo, in collaboration with Isokan Musulimi, organized peaceful demonstrations to contest these breaches, asserting the religious rights of Muslim students within the institution. The issue drew support from some Christian stakeholders who opposed the exclusive use of the campus for one denomination, highlighting concerns over fairness and interfaith equity³⁰.

This was eventually addressed through a government-led reconciliation meeting, which brought together the university management, Ta'awun officials, and notable Islamic scholars.³¹

The 2005 Alágbàá Masquerade Incident and The Jam'at Ta'awunil-Muslimin, Iwo

The Jam'at Ta'awunil-Muslimin is widely recognized in Iwo and environs as an Islamic organization committed to justice, equity, and protection of Muslim rights. Its interventions are generally motivated by acts of injustice or anti-Islamic aggression, rather than involvement in inter-religious disputes³².

In July/August 2005, a notable incident arose during the annual Eegun festival, involving a masquerade attributed to Alágbàá. During the procession, local thugs disrupted the event after being requested to provide financial contributions to the masquerade, beat up the masquerade and seized his regalia and money already contributed for him. In response, the Ta'awun intervened to protect the masquerade, ensuring his safety and handing over and his regalia to the police, thereby preventing further immediate harm, then Alágbàá, the custodian of the masquerade went to bail him out. The situation was later politicized by certain actors, who sought to portray the Ta'awun as aggressors against traditional worshippers. This narrative mobilized additional groups, including allies from Olólù in Ibadan, Oyo State, members of the Oodua People's Congress (OPC) from Lagos, and participants from neighboring towns, to confront the organization. The escalation culminated in an attack on the residence of the Ta'awun founder, prompting local Muslims and Isokan Musulimi members to mobilize in defense.

Amid the conflict, certain community members, acting independently and without directives from the Ta'awun, dismantled a shrine located at the palace, removed the idol *Ògún òde 'la* and deposited it into the nearby *Áígbàá* river. The situation necessitated police intervention, resulting in the arrest of several individuals, including seven Ta'awun members and the organization's vice president. The

conflict was resolved by the intervention of the state government, led by then-Governor Olagunsoye Oyinlola and Iwo traditional authorities.³³

Qamarudeen Islamic Society and Traditional Worshippers, Osogbo

The Qamarudeen Islamic Society in Osogbo is recognized for its strict monotheistic stance, encapsulated in the slogan “Kosebo kò s’ogun, Agbara t’Olohun ni” (No idolatry (Shirk), no magic or charm (Sihr); Allāh has the power) which is perceived as a threat to traditional worshippers, including some Muslims who practice syncretism, as it directly challenges the *ebo* system central to indigenous religious observance. The earliest recorded conflict between the Qamarudeen Islamic Society and traditional worshippers in Osogbo occurred in July 2004, when the masquerade Eegun Ogunleke and his followers attacked the Qamarudeen central mosque. The masquerade was unmasked, and the regalia was destroyed by the Muslims.

Police intervention led to arrests, and the case was brought before the magistrate court, where it was later adjourned. Subsequent reconciliation was facilitated by the Ataoja of Osogbo, involving structured restitution where the Traditional worshippers were represented by Chief Esuleke and the Muslims by the late Chief Imam of Osogbo, Alhaji Mustafa Ajisafe: the Osogbo Central mosque management contributed ₦100,000, the Ataoja ₦20,000, and the traditional worshippers ₦60,000, despite the estimated value of the destroyed Qamarudeen mosque properties exceeding the collective contributions. An undertaking was signed, including a pact not to engage in future confrontations³⁴

Despite this agreement, similar clashes resurfaced in 2018, involving less severe destruction of Mosque facilities. A more pronounced confrontation occurred in 2021 during a public program organized by the Qamarudeen Islamic Society. The 2021 incident involved the masquerade procession of Òpèké, associated with Chief Esuleke, a traditionalist and native doctor, carried by his son, Fashola Esuleke. The procession, escorted by the police at the request of Esuleke probably to protect members of the procession, passed near the residence of the Islamic Society.³⁵ As the procession advanced, members of the masquerade fired gunshots into the air and threw stones, disrupting the gathering. Members of the Islamic society, defending themselves, engaged in a confrontation that resulted in fatalities and injuries on both sides, including the death of Salahudeen Moshood, a member of the Islamic Society. The aftermath saw arrests of Esuleke and his followers, who were charged with murder.³⁶

The 2001 Ibrazul-Haq Da'wah Society Incident in Osogbo

The Ibrazul-Haq Da'wah Society of Nigeria, established by Alhaji Abdulfatah Jagunmolu, an extraction of Izharul-Haqq established by late Uztas Abdul Lateef

Adebowale, has historically been active in public preaching and Islamic propagation activities. In 2001, during a widely attended three-day open preaching program at Egbededo Street, Osogbo, coinciding with the international evangelist Reinhard Bonnke's crusade in the state, the gathering was violently disrupted where an unknown assailants threw petrol bombs at attendees, creating immediate disorder and panic. One individual, later identified as Sunday Aransiola, was apprehended after being chased from the scene who was in possession of dangerous weapons. In the process, he sustained serious physical assault before being handed over to the police by the leaders of Ibrazul-Haq. Tragically, the detainee died in police custody the following day, transforming the initial assault into a highly complex matter. Concurrently, other unknown actors engaged in attacks on local churches, intensifying perceptions of religiously motivated violence. The Amir of Ibrazul-Haq and one associate, AbdulRasheed Olohuntobi, were subsequently arrested and detained, spending approximately 64 days in remand before bail was granted. The case persisted for about five years before final resolution³⁷.

Religious Rivalry and Spatial Negotiation in Eḍe

Inter-religious dynamics in Eḍe town have historically been shaped by the negotiation of public spaces among Muslims, Christians, and traditional worshippers. These tensions intensified with the introduction of Christianity in the early 20th century, creating new layers of competition over education, ritual visibility, and moral authority. The rise of Islamic authority under the fourth king of Eḍe, Timi Lagunju, who, after embraced significantly altered the religious landscape by publicly declaring Islam as his preferred religion and integrating Shari'ah principles into governance, Timi Lagunju elevated Islamic moral and judicial standards in the town. This threatened the status and visibility of indigenous religious practices. Subsequent reigns, including that of Timi Tijani Oladokun Oyewusi (Agbonran II, 1976–2007), witnessed confrontations over the relocation of the Sango shrine, which had been placed at the center of the market near a Ratibi Mosque behind the Ede Central Mosque. Eminent Muslims, led by notable figures including Sheikh Salaudeen Olayiwola and Abdul-Ganiyu Olagunju, intervened to remove the statue to the palace, the Traditional worshippers protested the action but the issue was later resolved and the resolution has been operative till present day³⁸.

The introduction of Christian mission schools and Western education created strategic advantages for Christian converts, drawing communities toward mission-affiliated institutions. Muslims and Traditionalists, wary of conversion, often resisted attendance, which initially limited the Muslims' access to educational opportunities. In response, Muslim communities mobilized resources to establish Ede Muslim Grammar School, ensuring equitable access to education for the Muslims³⁹.

In July 2011, the Healing Jesus Crusade, organized by the Dag-Heward Mills Ministry of Ghana, prompted mass publicity and mobilization across Èdè, including banners, posters, and street parades. A section of the Muslim community, notably the *Tabligh Jama'at*, responded by organizing parallel vigils and displaying Islamic messages such as “Allah is the Healer, the Saviour and the Provider”. This episode exemplifies competitive religious public engagement, though notably, it did not escalate into violence⁴⁰.

Religious Encounters and Conflict Management in Ile-Ife

Ile-Ife, also in its abbreviated form, Ife, one of the major Yoruba historical and cultural cities, represents a distinctive case of longstanding inter-religious cohabitation, where many family compounds house Muslims alongside Christians or traditional worshippers. The devout yet tolerant nature of the Muslim community has contributed significantly to the relative absence of major inter-religious conflicts for ages. Historically, Muslims in Ife have avoided legal or palace confrontations over interfaith disputes, preferring dialogue and ethical engagement.

Minor tensions with Christians have occurred periodically. These include instances where Christian evangelists approached mosques during Salat (prayer) times to preach or sometimes conducted crusades near the Chief Imam's residence, often using bells with inscriptions such as “E gba Jesu sinu aye yin, Jesu ni Olugbala” (accept Jesus into your life as the Saviour). Additionally, some Christian teachers in public schools attempted to influence Muslim students to embrace Christianity, while government policies promoting the Hijab occasioned harassment of Muslim students. Such incidents were amicably resolved through intervention by the Chief Imam and coordination with the Chairman of the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN)⁴¹.

Historical engagement with traditional worshippers reveals the strategic use of religious authority and precedent to prevent escalation. Oral histories report that during the reign of Imam Raji' Ayinde (1834–1949), a Muslim who died by suicide became the center of a dispute over burial rites between Muslims and traditionalists. The Chief Imam cautioned that if traditionalists insisted on performing their rites, they would face the same fate. The traditionalist leader who proceeded eventually died in a similar manner. Recent disputes with traditional worshippers occurred due to the usual *Obàtálá* festival's imposition of curfews (Oro) that often conflict with Muslim prayer schedules. Intervention by the overall leader of traditional worshippers, Obàdio, prevented confrontation and ensured the Muslims could perform their Salat without obstruction. Similarly, the celebration of the *Gbànlàré* idol, which imposed a curfew on a Friday, was addressed promptly by the Chief Imam reporting to the traditional secretary of the Ooni, Oba Ogunwusi, leading to a caution that mitigated potential conflict⁴².

Despite general tolerance, violent incidents have occasionally occurred. On Thursday, 30th March 2023, during the 1444AH Ramadan, the Oro procession, announced in advance, and during their procession invaded Ìdí-Òmò Mosque. Traditionalists attacked Muslims, including the Imam, Alhaji Abdul Fatai Adesiyan, with machetes and other weapons while they were performing ablution and preparing for *Salat al 'asr* (evening prayer). In response, thousands of Ife Muslims staged a peaceful protest the following day, carrying placards with messages such as “*Stop imposition of idolatry in Ife*” and “*Islam is peace, Muslims are peaceful*”, demanding justice and highlighting the community’s commitment to non-violent resolution of interfaith conflicts⁴³.

Analysis of The Relevance of *Ṣulh*

The preference for amicable settlement over formal adjudication is deeply rooted in early Islamic legal thought and practice. A well-known report attributed to ‘Umar ibn al-Khaṭṭāb (RA), the second Rightly Guided Caliph, reflects this orientation toward reconciliation. He is reported to have advised: “Repel the disputants until they reconcile among themselves, for adjudication breeds rancour.” This statement encapsulates the early Islamic recognition that judicial verdicts, while legally binding, may exacerbate social tensions rather than resolve underlying grievances, particularly in disputes involving close social or communal ties. Classical juristic literature further underscores the normative and practical significance of *Ṣulh*. *Ibn Farḥūn*, a prominent Mālikī jurist, emphasized that judges should encourage amicable settlement in specific categories of disputes. These include cases where:

- (1) the disputing parties share kinship or close social relationships;
- (2) they are individuals of moral integrity and respected status within society;
- (3) there exists a likelihood that litigation would intensify hostility and social discord; and
- (4) the complexity or ambiguity of the dispute renders judicial determination particularly difficult⁴⁴.

Such juristic insights demonstrate that *Ṣulh* is not merely a discretionary option but a systematic legal strategy designed to balance justice with social harmony. Thus, in the context of interfaith conflicts in a multi religious society like Osun State, *Ṣulh* emerges as a particularly appropriate and effective mechanism of dispute resolution largely because inter-religious conflicts often arise among communities that share long-standing social, economic, historical, and cultural relationships prior to the eruption of disputes. Unlike adversarial litigation, which tends to entrench divisions and institutionalize antagonism. The cases of interfaith conflicts in Osun State highlight recurring patterns of tension between Muslims, Christians, and traditional worshippers, as well as the role of religious, political, and cultural actors in

mitigating such disputes. These cases are examined through the lens of the principles of *Ṣulh* for inter-faith conflict and analysed thematically.

Religious Pluralism

A recurring cause of interfaith conflict across the cases examined is the failure to recognise and respect religious plurality and freedom of conscience. *Ṣulh*, as an Islamic model of ADR presupposes the acknowledgment of religious diversity as a social reality and a moral necessity. This foundational principle aligns not only with Qur’anic ethics but also with Nigerian and international legal instruments.

Internationally, freedom of religion is guaranteed under Article 18 of the *Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948)* and Article 8 of the *African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights*. Domestically, Nigeria’s secular character is entrenched in Section 10 of the 1999 Constitution (as amended), which prohibits the adoption of any religion as a state religion, while Section 38(1) guarantees freedom of thought, conscience, religion, worship, and propagation. These provisions collectively affirm that no religious group may claim monopoly over public space or state authority.

Non-recognition of religion plurality is illustrated in Case 1, where the extension of the Eegun Ogundeji masquerade procession into predominantly Muslim areas of the *Qamarudeen* Islamic Society triggered violence. Similarly, Case 6 (Ede) demonstrates how historical tensions surrounding shrine locations, mosque proximity, and educational dominance reflected struggles over religious visibility and authority. These conflicts could have been mitigated through early affirmation of pluralism and negotiated spatial coexistence.

In contrast, Case 7 (Ile-Ife) exemplifies how long-standing recognition of religious plurality which is evident in mixed-faith family compounds and institutional restraint, this has contributed to relative interfaith stability for decades. These cases collectively affirm that recognition of religious diversity is the first and indispensable pillar of *Ṣulḥ* in pluralistic societies.

Symbolic Sensitivities

Preventive ethic of respect and non-provocation requires abstention from acts, symbols, or expressions likely to inflame religious sensitivities. Islam regards such restraint not merely as conflict resolution but as conflict prevention, consistent with Qur'anic guidance prohibiting insult to the sacred symbols of others (Q. 6:108) where Allah warns that:

وَلَا تَسُبُّوا الَّذِينَ يَدْعُونَ مِنْ دُونِ اللَّهِ فَيَسُبُّوا اللَّهَ عَدْوًا بِغَيْرِ عِلْمِكُمْ ذَلِكَ زَيْنًا لِكُلِّ أُمَّةٍ
عَمَلُهُمْ ثُمَّ إِلَىٰ رَبِّهِمْ مَرْجِعُهُمْ فَيُنَبِّئُهُمْ بِمَا كَانُوا يَعْمَلُونَ

And do not insult those they invoke other than Allāh, lest they insult Allāh in enmity without knowledge. Thus We have made pleasing to every community their deeds. Then to their Lord is their return, and He will inform them about what they used to do.

This ethical imperative finds resonance in Nigerian law. *Section 204* of the *Criminal Code Act* and corresponding provisions of the *Penal Code* criminalise acts intended or likely to insult religious sentiments and provoke breach of public peace, reflecting the state's interest in maintaining communal order rather than adjudicating theological truth. This legal framework parallels the *Ṣulḥ* objective of preventing escalation through responsible conduct.

Several cases illustrate the consequences of neglecting this principle. In Case 1, the ringing of a bell which is symbolically associated with a rival and hostile masquerade was perceived as deliberate provocation, precipitating violent retaliation. In Case 4, the convergence of a masquerade procession within a major Islamic gathering, accompanied by gunshots and stone-throwing, transformed a latent tension into a deadly confrontation.

Conversely, Case 7 demonstrates the efficacy of preventive ethics. In Ile-Ife, the Chief Imam's proactive engagement with palace authorities regarding *Oro* curfews and festival timings prevented repeated religious activities from clashing with Muslim prayer schedules. This anticipatory restraint reflects the essence of *Ṣulḥ* as a mechanism for averting conflict before it materialises.

Peaceful Negotiation

In pluralistic societies, interfaith friction may be inevitable; what distinguishes sustainable coexistence is the willingness of parties to incline toward peace rather than retaliation. Preference for peaceful settlement and a sincere commitment to reconciliation once conflict arises is evident in several cases where reconciliation mechanisms proved effective. In Case 2, the dispute between Muslim stakeholders and Bowen University authorities over breached religious agreements was resolved through state-facilitated reconciliation involving religious leaders and institutional representatives. This process underscores the viability of negotiated settlement over adversarial litigation.

Similarly, Case 3 illustrates how a violent escalation involving the *Jamā'at Ta'awunil-Muslimīn* and traditional worshippers was ultimately resolved through government mediation and palace involvement, reinforcing reconciliation over prolonged hostility. In Case 5, despite the severity of the attack on the *Ibrahim-Haq Da'wah* Society, the leadership's decision to hand over the suspect to law enforcement and pursue legal redress rather than vigilante retaliation.

Historically, Case 7 further shows that in Ile-Ife, disputes ranging from evangelistic encroachments to burial controversies were repeatedly resolved through dialogue and mediation by religious and traditional authorities, preventing cyclical violence. These examples collectively affirm that the durability of peace depends on an explicit commitment to reconciliation, even after wrongdoing.

Dialogical Engagement

Qur'anic injunctions (Q. 3:64; 16:125; 29:46) establish dialogue as the preferred mode of engagement with religious others, particularly in contexts of disagreement. Dialogue transforms conflict from confrontation into communication and enables negotiated compromise.

Empirically, this principle is most visible where neutral intermediaries facilitated discussion. In Case 4, repeated clashes in Osogbo prompted palace-mediated dialogue that included restitution payments, written undertakings, and formal pledges, reflecting structured *Ṣulḥ* processes akin to Qur'anic arbitration (Q. 4:35). Although recurrence indicates partial failure, the dialogical framework itself proved indispensable. In Case 7, institutionalised dialogue between the Chief Imam of Ile-Ife, the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN), and palace authorities consistently

resolved tensions over evangelism, school policies, and festival practices without violence.

At the national and international levels, bodies such as the *Nigeria Inter-Religious Council (NIREC)* and the King Abdullah Bin Abdulaziz International Centre for Interreligious and Intercultural Dialogue (*KAICIID*) embody this *Ṣulḥ*-oriented dialogical approach, reinforcing its contemporary relevance. These cases demonstrate that ethical dialogue is not peripheral but central to *Ṣulḥ*, particularly in societies where religious spaces, symbols, and identities intersect.

Conclusion

This study has examined *Ṣulḥ* as a culturally grounded Islamic model for managing inter-faith crises within pluralistic societies, using Osun State, Nigeria, as a case study. Drawing on the Qur'ān provisions, *Sunnah*, and Islamic legal thought, and corroborated by qualitative evidence from inter-religious conflict cases, the paper demonstrates that inter-faith tensions are often less a product of theological incompatibility than of contested spaces, symbolic provocation, institutional breaches, and failures of communication.

This study presents *Ṣulḥ* as a post-conflict mechanism and a preventive and transformative process, structured around four interdependent principles: recognition of religious plurality and freedom of conscience; ethical restraint and non-provocation; preference for peaceful settlement and reconciliation; and dialogical engagement. Where these principles were informally or institutionally applied, conflicts were de-escalated and social relations restored. Conversely, their absence or distortion contributed to recurrent violence and unresolved grievances.

By mapping these principles onto lived inter-faith encounters in Osun State, the paper advances an empirically informed model of Islamic ADR that complements constitutional guarantees of religious freedom and existing state-based dispute resolution mechanisms. In doing so, it challenges reductive portrayals of Islamic law as inherently adversarial and demonstrates its relevance to contemporary peacebuilding in multi-religious societies.

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